

THEORETICAL BASICS OF YOUTH SOCIAL MOBILITY RESEARCH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12525803>

Abstract: This article discusses the socialization and innovative activity of young people in today's global modernization process, personal characteristics, thoughts and opinions of young people, independent thinking skills in the world of science and society development today.

Key words: society, social development, modernization, innovation, ethical rules, education, skills, personal characteristics, independent thinking, ability.

In the system of comprehensive social development spheres, the issue of providing modern education and social support to young people is of particular importance due to its acuteness and relevance. After all, it is known from history that in every period it was enlightenment that gave impetus to the welfare of the society and the development of the country. For this reason, the issue of transferring the saying of our wise people, "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave" to our practical life, and implementing the principle of continuity of education in our country, is rising to the level of state policy. In the last two years, large-scale measures have been taken to bring the education system up to the level of modern democracies, to further increase the position of young people in our society as the leading force of development. Further improvement of the higher education system has become an important direction of reforms in the social sphere. In particular, the program for the comprehensive development of the higher education system was adopted in 2017-2021. Transparent mechanisms for admission to higher education institutions were introduced and quotas were seriously increased. New, modern educational institutions, including branches of prestigious foreign universities, are being established in the higher education system. Due to newly established institutes and branches, the number of higher education institutions in our country has reached 81, regional branches have reached 15, and foreign university branches have reached 7. Correspondence and evening departments were opened in higher education institutions.

As the head of our state Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted, "We have a single goal in mind from all of this. That is, Uzbekistan must be globally competitive in terms of science, intellectual potential, modern personnel, and high technologies." In the Presidential Address, as an important practical step to ensure that the field of education directly serves human development, the level of preschool education coverage of children from 34 percent to 44 percent in 2019, the

establishment of a modern general secondary education system, private schools based on the principles of public-private partnership and the main attention is being paid to the creation of kindergartens and the creation of equal opportunities for studying in the higher education system. In particular, in the last two years, the level of coverage of graduates of higher and secondary special education institutions with higher education has been increased from 9-10 percent to 15 percent. In this regard, in the Address of the President, in 2019, the task was set to increase the level of coverage of graduates with higher education in our country to 20% and to increase it in the coming years.

The social sphere is one of the most complex spheres in the life of society. Because it reflects all the factors related not only to people's living. At the same time, the mood of people also affects the directions of relations in the life of society. The social sphere is the creation of a family, giving birth to a child, bringing it up to serve the society, country, nation and people, providing employment (employment) of citizens, getting quality education, being able to enjoy medical services, between different classes, social groups and ethnic groups in society. It covers harmony, stability of religious tolerance, the existence of necessary conditions for the implementation of national customs, traditions and values, the development of science, technology and technology and their effective use for people to live a prosperous life.

Social-innovative activity - ensures the sustainable development of the networks of the social structure of the society. One of the leading forces in this process is the youth. It should be noted that today's youth of our country have their worldview, their desire for innovation and creativity, their independent views on the processes taking place in our society, our country and the world, their desire to solve the difficulties and problems that arise in their lives, relying on their own strength and labor talent, which are their predecessors of the former Union period. they are completely different from their youth. It is worth noting that the young generations of New Uzbekistan, which is being built over the next 4-5 years, are being formed. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev wrote in his "New Uzbekistan Strategy" as follows: "Strengthening the civic position and activity of the young generation, raising our children to be independent thinkers, well-rounded individuals and mature professionals who can compete in the international arena, thoroughly acquiring modern knowledge and skills. We are carrying out large-scale work»[1]. As a result of this, today our young people are forming as new generations of New Uzbekistan by mastering modern science, technology, technologies, applying them to serve

the development of our country, taking the lead among their peers in education at famous higher educational institutions, and preserving national and universal values. Their independent courage, the most important thing is that they are emerging as new generations of New Uzbekistan with the development of their outlook and thinking in line with the processes taking place in the world and in our country. Motives that encourage them to lead are expressed in society, such as the youth power of the population, a desire for innovation and a tendency to creativity. These characteristics serve as the main factor in the creation and implementation of innovations in the fields in which they operate.

During the years of independence, a new generation of young people was formed in Uzbekistan, they make a worthy contribution to our development with their desire for innovation, their efforts to master the field of science, technology and technology. According to the information provided by the Central Council of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, today in our country there are 17,913,815 young people under the age of 30, and 9,513,578 young people between the ages of 14 and 30. Among them, 6,945 young people engaged in farming make up 0.04 percent, and 62,921 young people engaged in entrepreneurship make up 0.35 percent.

If we analyze the given figures, this indicator cannot be considered satisfactory. But if we take into account that the interest in farming and entrepreneurship is increasing day by day, it is clear that there are opportunities for these indicators to grow significantly. These areas are new directions in the independent activities of our youth. They got this opportunity only thanks to independence. Until 1991, young people were engaged in farming only on the basis of following orders from above, and negative attitudes were formed regarding entrepreneurship as "buying and selling". Even today, it is true to say that we have not completely gotten rid of these negative relations. Because the inertia of negative relationships remains in the minds of our youth. Moreover, the development of these fields in our country, the formation of skills for using the created opportunities, lags far behind the growing needs of the field.

The participation of our youth in innovative processes in the field of science, technology and technology is also increasing year by year. In order to support innovative processes, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 No. PF-5544 "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021" was announced. The decree states that "the low level of cooperation between the economic and social sphere networks and scientific institutions, the insufficient

coordination of the activities of the ministries and departments, as well as the local state authorities in the field of innovative development does not allow to achieve the first priority goals and tasks in this regard" and in order to solve the problem, the strategy the main tasks are defined.

Among other things, it is written that "Development of human capital as the main factor determining the level of competitiveness of the country in the international arena and its innovative development is the main goal of the strategy." Young people are part of this capital. In this sense, the development of innovative thinking in the minds, worldviews and practical activities of young people allows for the effective implementation of the tasks defined in the decree. The active participation of our youth in the implementation of the tasks specified in the decree ensures the effective implementation of decisions. Without the active participation of young people in innovative processes, the tasks facing our development cannot be solved positively. In our opinion: a) formation of innovative thinking among young people; b) development of their intellectual potential at the level of contemporary requirements; c) to achieve socialization in the society, that is, to strengthen cooperation with different social groups and classes towards a common goal; g) to achieve materially specific provision of innovative ideas; d) the issue of organizing the implementation of the created innovative ideas is facing us.

So what does innovation have to do with thinking? "Thinking is the highest form of perception of the objective world; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. In the process of thinking, thoughts, opinions, ideas, hypotheses, etc. are formed in a person and they are expressed in the mind of a person in the form of concepts, judgments, and conclusions. Thought appears in the process of people's social production... creative works, discoveries, inventions, proposals are the product of thinking»[2].

It is known that only a person with high thinking can form innovative ideas, new thoughts and understand their importance in practice. Ideas, discoveries, and great works of the peoples of the world related to national and universal development are the product of high thinking. Philosophy, which encourages a person to become a true person, and embodies reflections, views and ideas about the solutions to the puzzles before him, is also considered a product of thinking. So, it can be said that innovation and thinking are two sides of the coin. Just as innovation cannot be imagined without thinking, thinking cannot be imagined without innovation. It follows that social activity can be developed in young people only by developing innovative thinking. Such

thinking is not formed by itself, but the environment in the family, father and mother's interest in novelty, various events and processes that occur in life, and the tendency to search for solutions have a positive effect. At the same time, another factor of the formation and development of innovative thinking is the desire of young people to read and study works of art and create the necessary conclusions. So what are the main problems in this direction? On the one hand, today, when the need for innovative ideas and inventions is increasing, the interest of young people in art and works of art is "fading", on the other hand, it is worrying that their place is being taken by the Internet, mobile phone and mass communication technologies in this direction. By reading a book, a person can think about events and processes, get good conclusions and new ideas. Mass media "mechanically" convey events or processes to a person, but do not "leave" time for observation, its speed cannot provide the spiritual nourishment that you get from reading a book. Anyway, these virtual ideas are becoming popular among young people.

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